

OPTIMISM AND CONFLICT MANAGEMENT STYLES: CONSTRUCTIVE HUMOR AS A MEDIATOR

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ABSTRACT

The present study aimed to investigate the connection between optimism, constructive humor and conflict management styles. The sample consisted of 200 participants aged 18 to 25 years (Mean=21.30, SD=2.059) collected through convenience sampling technique. Three scales were used for data collection, i.e., Conflict Management Style Assessment Scale (Adkins, 2004), Humor Style Questionnaire (HSQ; Martin et al., 2003), and Revised Life Orientation Scale (Scheier, Carver, & Bridges, 1994). The study assumed a positive impact of optimism on conflict management styles and a constructive humor as a mediator between optimism and conflict management styles. The results showed that optimism explained 8% of variance in conflict management styles, hence showing its positive impact on conflict management. Additionally, constructive humor partially mediated between constructive humor and conflict management styles. The study highlights that the use of positive thinking and constructive humor may improve interpersonal conflicts.

Keywords: Optimism, conflict management styles, humor

INTRODUCTION

As social interactions become increasingly dynamic, the ability to manage interpersonal conflict effectively is more essential than ever. Conflicts naturally emerge in personal, professional, and social contexts due to differing goals, perspectives, or emotional tension (De Dreu & Gelfand, 2008). McCroskey and Wheelless's (1976) early framework described conflict as a sign of relational deterioration,

where initial connection gives way to emotional distance, mutual dislike, and reduced trust. These tensions, are often accompanied by anger, frustration, and defensiveness (Jehn, 1995) that can appear in various domains but also offer opportunities for growth, understanding, and strengthened relationships when managed constructively (Rahim, 2002). Conflict is neutral in nature; its effects depend on how it is

handled, either as a source of harm or a catalyst for growth. Thus, effective conflict management aims to resolve differences constructively, balancing the needs of all involved. Conflict management styles refer to the way people approach and handle their conflicts (Herrity, 2025). Based on Thomas and Killman Model (1974), four types of conflict management styles are more popular comprising avoiding, accommodating, competing, and collaborating. Each style is the combination of the dimension of cooperative vs noncooperative and assertive vs non-assertive: avoiding and accommodating is non-assertive type with avoiding as uncooperative and accommodating as cooperating. Similarly, competing and collaborating are assertive types with competing as noncooperative and collaborating as cooperative. Compromising is using moderate amount of both assertiveness and cooperation. There can be many psychological and emotional factors apart from communication skills that can help in conflict resolution; two such underexplored yet powerful tools are optimism and constructive humor, which can reshape how conflicts unfold and are resolved.

Optimism, defined as the expectation that positive outcomes will occur, plays a central role in how individuals interpret and respond to stress and conflict (Scheier & Carver, 1985). Optimists maintain greater psychological well-being, even in high-stress situations, regardless of prior emotional states. Studies show that optimism is linked to active, engagement-focused coping and lower reliance on avoidant strategies (Peterson, 2000; Nes & Segerstrom, 2006), fostering emotional regulation and healthier communication (Carver, Scheier, & Segerstrom, 2010). In social interactions, optimism often leads to a more collaborative and less confrontational tone, reducing interpersonal tension (Segerstrom, 2006). It also supports constructive conflict resolution approaches, such as compromise and collaboration, instead of aggression or avoidance

(Carver & Scheier, 2014). Optimists are more likely to view interpersonal issues as temporary and manageable, lowering emotional reactivity and promoting solution-focused behaviours.

Similarly, humor is also considered as yielding beneficial psychological results. Humor maintains long standing relationships exciting, refreshing, and lively and may also help dealing with conflicts, differences as well as minor grievances that can weaken even the strongest bonds (Robinson, Segal, & Smith, n.d). According to Kyomugisha (2025) humor may serve as a significant coping mechanism which can reduce the negative impact of calamities, decrease stress, and develops resilience. In a recent study (Liao et al, 2025) adaptive humor predicted wellbeing, hence playing its role in enhancing subjective happiness. Likewise, Fry (1995) highlighted strong links between humor, optimism, and coping strategies. Yue, Hao, and Goldman (2010) further demonstrated that people who use adaptive humor styles tend to be more optimistic, while those using maladaptive humor report lower optimism. Adaptive styles, such as affiliative and self-enhancing humor, are positively correlated with optimism, while aggressive or self-defeating humor is negatively associated (Yue et al., 2010). Interest in humor's psychological role has grown steadily since the 20th century (Martin, 1998), with increasing focus on its positive contributions to mental and physical health (Lefcourt, 2001; Martin, 2001). Humor serves to regulate emotions, foster social bonds, and build group cohesion (Martin, 2007). Constructive humor, in particular, refers to inclusive, positive humor that reduces stress and strengthens interpersonal connection. Research shows it fosters empathy, lowers emotional strain, and reframes negative exchanges in a more positive light (Martin, 2007; Cann et al., 1999). Unlike aggressive or self-defeating humor, constructive humor promotes emotional bonding and helps shift focus from problems to potential solutions during conflict (Romero & Pescosolido, 2008). When well-

timed and sensitively delivered, it can make individuals feel heard and understood, increasing willingness to compromise (Kuiper, Grimshaw, Leite, & Kirsh, 2004). Although forced humor along with sarcasm, and offensive jokes can have negative impact (Acharaya, 2024). It also acts as a cognitive reappraisal tool (Anerella, 2022) helping reframe threats in less distressing ways (Samson & Gross, 2012). Individuals who employ both optimism and constructive humor tend to exhibit stronger emotional regulation, empathy, and social competence which are key assets in resolving conflict effectively (Lyubomirsky, 2001).

Rationale of study

Recent research highlights that optimism and constructive humor not only benefit individuals independently but also interact synergistically. While prior studies have linked optimism to adaptive coping, emotional resilience, and interpersonal success (Scheier & Carver, 1985; Carver et al., 2010), and constructive humor to reduced tension and stronger social bonds (Martin, 2007; Cann, Zapata & Davis, 1999), their combined effect on interpersonal conflict remains underexplored. Based on Fry (1995) and Yue et al. (2010) work, this study examines how optimism and constructive humor jointly influence conflict outcomes. It proposes a mediating model where constructive humor explains how optimism mitigates negative conflict experiences by focusing on this interaction and its role in conflict. As Pakistan is a collectivistic culture, building positive relations is very important here. According to Kyomugisha (2025), variations exist in the expression of humor worldwide, its expression changes according to the ethnicity and nationality of the individual. Individuals act according to their cultural norms which monitor the expression of humor. Similar kind of humorous expressions bridges the gap among individuals that enhances community engagement. Likewise, laughing together may

lessen the inter-group tension. Having the similar understanding of humorous dialogue may increase bonding among diverse groups of people. The study offers fresh insights for enhancing relationships via proper conflict management strategies and incorporating humor in our personal and professional life. Acharya (2024) has highlighted that humor will play its role when it has shared cultural understanding and is not used in power imbalance situation, which is more specific to Eastern societies.

Objectives

1. To investigate whether high levels of optimism and constructive humor are associated with a reduction in the negative outcomes of interpersonal conflicts.
2. To determine whether constructive humor mediates the relationship between optimism and interpersonal conflict.

Hypotheses

1. Optimism has a positive impact on conflict management styles.
2. Constructive humor will mediate the relationship between optimism and conflict management styles.

METHOD

Sample

The sample of the study consisted of 200 participants, with an equal number of 100 males and 100 females between age range of 18 to 25 years (Mean=21.30, SD=2.059). Data was collected from students enrolled in various educational programs in Pakistan using a convenience sampling method. Educational background was as follows: 1.5% Matric, 32.3% FA/FS.c, 58.2% undergraduate, 7.5% graduate, and 0.5% postgraduate (MPhil/PhD). Regarding age, 78 participants (38.8%) were between 18 to 20 years, 87 (43.3%) between 21 to 23 years, and 36 (17.9%) were in 24 to 25 age range.

Instruments

Apart from the demographic Sheet (that asked about participants' age, gender, and educational qualification); the Conflict Management Style Assessment Scale, the Humor Style Questionnaire, and the Revised Life Orientation Scale were used in the study.

Conflict Management Style Assessment Scale

The Conflict Management Styles Assessment scale was developed by Adkins(2004) to evaluate how individuals handle interpersonal conflict. It is based on Thomas and Kilmann's (1974) model. It includes 15 items rated on a 4-point Likert scale(1=rarely,4=Always), covering five styles: Collaborating (items 1, 5, 7), Competing (4,9,11), Avoiding (6,10,15), Accommodating (3, 8,14), and Compromising (2, 12,13). Each style's score is the sum of its three items, with higher scores reflecting stronger preference. This study found a Cronbach's alpha of 0.614, indicating moderate internal consistency. Prior research supports the scale's test-retest reliability (Rahim & Bonoma, 1979). Its brief format and strong theoretical basis make it useful across various settings for improving conflict resolution.

Humor Style Questionnaire

The Humor Styles Questionnaire (HSQ; Martin et al. (2003), evaluates individual differences in humor across four styles: affiliative, self-enhancing, aggressive, and self-defeating. Affiliative and self-enhancing humor are considered constructive, as they promote relationships and coping, while aggressive and self-defeating humor are maladaptive and can harm oneself or others. The 32-item questionnaire uses a 7-point Likert scale, with eight items per style. In this study, the reliability was moderate (Cronbach's α =.671),although the original subscales showed good internal consistency:Affiliative(α =.80),Self-Enhancing(α =.81),Aggressive(α =.77),and Self-Defeating(α =.80).Test-retest reliability is

moderate to high (Martin et al., 2003). The HSQ also demonstrates strong construct validity, correlating humor styles with personality, well-being, and social outcomes. Constructive humor is linked to resilience and emotional intelligence, while maladaptive humor correlates with relational and emotional difficulties (Kuiper et al., 2004).

Revised Life Orientation Scale (LOT-R)

The Revised Life Orientation Test (LOT-R),developed by Scheier, Carver, and Bridges (1994), measures dispositional optimism, which refers to the expectation of positive future outcomes, based on expectancy-value theory. The 10-item scale includes 4 optimism items, 4 pessimism items (reverse-scored), and 2 filler items,rated on a 5-point Likert scale(1=strongly disagree,5=strongly agree), with scores ranging from 0 to 24. Higher optimism subscale scores reflect a more positive outlook, while higher pessimism scores indicate a more negative view. In this study, the LOT-R demonstrated moderate internal consistency (Cronbach's α =.527), although prior research shows good test-retest reliability (.70-.80). The scale also has strong validity, correlating significantly with self-esteem, depression, coping, and the original LOT (95).

Procedure

This study used a convenience sampling method to collect data from individuals aged 18-25.A Google Form containing informed consent, demographic items, and three standardized instruments: the Conflict Management Style Assessment Scale, the Humor Style Questionnaire, and the Revised Life Orientation Test (LOT-R) were distributed via WhatsApp and other online platforms. In addition, printed questionnaires were provided in educational institutions for in-person responses. Over several weeks,200 completed surveys were gathered, including 132 online and 68 physical forms. Participation was voluntary,

and informed consent was obtained from all participants. The data were then entered into

SPSS for statistical analysis to test the study's hypotheses.

RESULTS

Table 1 Psychometric Properties for HSQ, CMS and LOT-R scales

Scale	No of Items	M	S.D	Range	Cronbach's Alpha
HSQ	32	133.03	18.11	95-218	.671
CMS	15	38.77	6.10	23-60	.614
LOTR	10	25.55	5.62	12-42	.527

Note. .HSQ=Humor Style Questionnaire, CMS=Conflict Management Scale, LOT-R=Revised Life Orientation Test

Table 1 presents the psychometric properties of the three scales used in the study. All the study scales showed acceptable reliability indices, i.e.,

HSQ yielded .67 coefficient alpha, CMS as .614 and LOT-R .52 coefficient.

Table 2 Simple Linear Regression Analysis Showing Optimism as Predictor of Conflict Management Styles

Variable	B	SE	β	T	P
Constant	30.96	1.963	—	15.99	.000
Optimism	.306	.074	.282	4.133	.000
R ²	.080				

Note. B = Unstandardized Coefficient, SE = Coefficient's Standard Error, β = Standardized Coefficient

Table 2 displays the results of a simple regression analysis examining the effects of optimism on conflict management styles. The model explains 8% of the variance in mental well-being (R² =

.80), with optimism (β = .23, p < .001) as a significant positive predictor of conflict management styles.

Table 3 Mediation Analyses of Constructive Humor as a mediator between Optimism and Conflict Management Styles

Variables	Model 1		Model 2			
	B	95% CI	B	95% CI		
		LL	UL		LL	UL
Constant	106.03***	94.90	117.16	23.25***	17.03	29.46
Optimism (LOTR)	1.057***	0.63	1.48	0.23**	0.077	0.37
Constructive Humor (HSQ)				0.072**	0.026	0.11
R ²	0.107			0.120		
F	23.98**			13.60***		

Note. Indirect Effect B=0.0769; 95% CI (.0132,1735); **p<.01,

According to table 3 the findings reveal that optimism explained 10.75% of the variation in constructive humor without taking into account the mediator, $F(1,199)=23.9782, p<.001$ (shown in model 1). In model 2 the mediator plays its role and both variables combined cause 12.08% of change in interpersonal conflicts of students, $F(2, 198)=13.6053, p<.001$. As the confidence interval do not have zero, which demonstrates that interpersonal conflicts is indirectly affected by optimism through constructive humor, $B=.0769, CI(.0132, .1735)$.

DISCUSSION

The present study investigated the impact of optimism and constructive humor on interpersonal conflicts among Pakistani students. The first hypothesis suggested that high levels of optimism would reduce interpersonal conflicts. Simple regression analysis (Table 2) revealed that optimism ($\beta=.28, p<.001$) significantly positively predicted conflict management abilities, explaining 8% of the variance in conflict management styles ($R=.080$). The result indicates that individuals with higher levels of optimism possess better conflict management skills. This finding aligns with prior research suggesting that optimism fosters constructive conflict resolution strategies, such as collaboration and compromise (Carver & Scheier, 2014). Optimistic individuals tend to view interpersonal challenges as temporary and manageable, which reduces emotional reactivity and prevents conflict escalation (Scheier & Carver, 1985).

The second hypothesis proposed that constructive humor would mediate the relationship between optimism and interpersonal conflicts. The direct effect of optimism on conflict management styles, controlling for constructive humor was significant ($B=.229, p<.0032$). Mediation analysis (Table 3) supported this hypothesis, revealing that optimism indirectly influenced interpersonal conflicts through constructive

humor ($B=.0769, 95\% CI [.0132, .1735]$). Initially, optimism explained 10.75% of the variation in constructive humor ($F(1,199)=23.9782, p<.001$). When constructive humor was introduced as a mediator, both variables together accounted for 12.08% of the variance in interpersonal conflicts ($F(2,198)=13.6053, p<.001$). These findings deepen our understanding of how optimism impacts conflict outcomes by identifying constructive humor as an explanatory mechanism. It suggests that optimistic individuals are more likely to use constructive humor, which, in turn, improves their ability to manage interpersonal conflicts. According to Acharya (2024) humor can be used to resolve interpersonal conflicts as it serves as an ice breaker which creates an emotional distance from the issue and reframes it in a lighter perspective which breaks the negative thought patterns, hence improving interpersonal relations. This mediation pathway aligns with Fry's (1995) research on the links between humor, optimism, and coping strategies, as well as Yue et al.'s (2010) findings on the relationship between adaptive humor styles and optimism. Cekrlija et al (2025) also found different humor styles and their results largely confirmed the positive association between optimism, humor styles and quality of life. Pasupuleti (2021) studied the role of humor in conflict management styles among IT professional and found that affiliative and self-enhancing humor had a significant positive association with solution-oriented conflict management style. Similarly, the positive association between constructive humor and conflict management supports Martin's (2007) view that appropriate humor can diffuse tension and shift focus from problems to solutions. These psychological traits appear to function as protective factors in conflict situations by promoting adaptive responses, rather than preventing conflicts altogether.

The mediating role of constructive humor can be explained through several mechanisms. First, it helps individuals regulate emotions during conflicts, allowing them to respond adaptively (Samson & Gross, 2012). Second, humor fosters empathy and social bonding, creating a more collaborative environment for resolution (Romero & Pescosolido, 2008). Third, it enables optimistic individuals to reframe conflicts as challenges, not threats (Kuiper et al., 2004). The findings support the positive impact of optimism and constructive humor on conflict management, filling a gap in prior research by identifying humor as a mediator. These results align with positive psychology frameworks that emphasize the role of emotions and cognitive styles in resilience (Lyubomirsky, 2001), highlighting the interactive nature of optimism and humor.

Conclusion

In practical terms, promoting optimism and constructive humor in educational settings could enhance conflict resolution skills, particularly for Pakistani students aged 18-25. In organizations, a positive, humor-inclusive culture could improve conflict management. Training should incorporate humor as a tool alongside traditional communication strategies.

Limitations and Suggestions

Despite its contributions, the study has limitations, including reliance on self-report measures and moderate reliability of the LOT-R scale. Future research could benefit from observational methods, culturally adapted of scales, and longitudinal designs to strengthen causal inferences. Research should include diverse age groups, cultures, and additional mediators, such as emotional intelligence, that could further clarify the pathways linking optimism to conflict outcomes. In conclusion, this study confirms that optimism and constructive humor positively impact conflict management, with humor acting as a mediator.

The findings offer insights for improving conflict resolution in educational and organizational settings. Future research should address study limitations and explore additional variables to refine strategies for fostering constructive interpersonal interactions.

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